

DEDICATION TO MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA

Tashkent State transport University

Mamurova Feruza Islamovna

Aktamova Aziza Utkir kizi

Annotation: about the life and work of Maqsum Shaykhzoda, about his entry into Uzbekistan and acquaintance with the famous writers here, about his creations during the war years. His works embody the floral echo of a burning soul, which lived with great revolutionary ideals, vivid patriotic feelings, truly creative emotions

Keywords: Maqsum Shaykhzadeh, life, creativity, famous, writers, creativity, works, great, patriotic.

Maqsum Maqsumbek Oglu Shaykhzadeh () (1908.25.10 (7.11), Republic of Azerbaijan, Ganja region, Aktosh Shaykhzoda — 1967.19.2, Tashkent) — poet, playwright, literary critic, translator, educator. Honored art figure in Uzbekistan. Graduated from doril-teacher in Baku. Initially, he worked as a teacher at the L-stage Azerbaijani school in Darband, the Technical School of Education and upbringing in the neck. He was arrested in 1927 as a member of the counter-revolutionary organization and exiled to Tashkent in February 1928. After a short period of study (1928) at the East FTI of the University of Central Asia in shaikhzo, "the truth of the East" (1929-32), "Red Uzbekistan", "yosh leninchi" gaz.lari (1932), served on the editorial boards of "Gulistan" magazine (1933-34). At the moment he worked as a researcher at the Institute of language and literature (1935-38). From 1938 until the end of his life, he first had an evening, then a daytime ped. Inlarida lectured on the history of Uzbek literature.

The first collection of poems - "worthy guard". This was followed by city's "ten poems", "My consonants", "book Three", "Republic", "twelve", "new devon", "election songs", "wrestling nechun?", "Battle and song", "Heart says...", "a notebook of fifteen years", "Land Poems", "the ToRs of time", "my applause", "years and roads", "poems", and other poetry collections have been published. In the early work of Shahi, and in part in some of his poems of the 50s, melodies characteristic of Azerbaijani poetry, signs of pulpit poetry were prioritized. But as the Shaykhzoda acquired the language and style of Uzbek classical and modern poetry, the Uzbek musical fluency in his poems went to kuchaya. The sheikhzoda, striving to actively react to reality, paid special attention to the description of important events that took

place in the life of the people and the country, the creation of the image of the heroes of Labor and struggle. To this end, he took the epic genre and wrote lyrical works such as "Uncle property", "the lamp", "Uncle", "inheritance", "The Story of the Hunter", "Alexander The Great", "The Eleven", "Zhenya", "The Elder", "the wisdom of Akhmadjan", "the third son", "the dream of the Nurmat father". One of the important qualities inherent in both the poet's poetry of the 30s and 40s and his later work is plot. As a poet inclined to create a lyrical plot, shaykhzoda turned to the pages of folk legends and historical past, as well as the lives of contemporaries, bringing to his poems poetic characters and various poetic details characteristic of the ballad, taking measures to increase the position of the word in the poetic device. At the same time Shaykhzoda discovered the new artistic possibilities of krfia, bringing into Uzbek poetry new manifestations of weight and form. This principle inherent in the work of the poet was vividly expressed in his, especially in the lyrical epic "Tashkent". The ruler of Turon was born in Sultonia during the five-year Wars of Amir Temur. His father was Shahrukh Mirzo and his mother was Gavharshod begim, a Turkic tribal Noble. He was given the name Mirza Muhammad Taragai. Ulugbek was not originally a name, but a pseudonym meaning " great ruler (bek)". Ulugbek was mentored by the poet and scholar Orif Azari.

As a child, he traveled through much of the Middle East and India, as his grandfather expanded the conquests in these areas. Temür gave control of Sayram, Auli-ota and the eastern territories to his grandson Mirzo Ulughbek before his campaign against China in 1404.

After Temür's death, Shohrukh moved the imperial capital to Herat (in what is now Afghanistan).

Coins minted on behalf of Ulugbek, 1448-1449, Herat

The 16-year-old Ulughbek later became governor of Samarkand in 1409. In 1411, he was proclaimed governor of all of Movarounnahr. In practice, however, her father in Herat was subject to the authority of Shahrukh Mirzo.

The teenage ruler aimed to make the city the intellectual center of the Empire. In 1417-1420, he built a madrasa ("University") on the Registan Square in Samarkand and invited many Islamic astronomers and mathematicians to study. Ulugbek's most famous pupil in astronomy was Ali Qushchi (d.1474). In kazizo, Rumi was the most prominent teacher of Ulughbek madrasa, and later the astronomer Jamshid al-Koshiy came to this place[11]

Ulugbek is famous in the world of science as a great astronomer. The greatest work he has done in this regard is the astronomical table called "Ziji jadidi Koragani". Ulugbek was also interested in medicine and music, and wrote poetry. Shaikhzoda stood out from all of us not only in the sense of reason, but also in the sense of siymo. The idle question of the autonomous mouth did not seem to melt into it. On the contrary, everywhere, all the time, in all environments and conditions, the feeling of pride, which has made his heart prosperous, has been exasperated. He leaned, even proud, and said that he was Azerbaijani, coming from Azerbaijan. While reciting the same words, Maqsud's face seemed as if the sun in the sky had moved (Maqsud from a page of memoirs about the Sheikhzoda).

Maqsud Shaykhzoda died on February 19, 1967. He was buried in the chigatoy cemetery. Awarded the order of merit (2001). One of the streets in Tashkent is named after Shaykhzoda.

There will be lifetimes,

Alive is dead.

There will be deaths,

The dead man is alive.

Uzbekistan

Air that is also stored in a closed crate,

But the air breath that he lost,

To say it air, noravo himself,

The Bandit chokes longing.

He is a carefree, innocent, like a dead wine,

Neither drunkenness nor excitement.

Whereas, in a free flight,

Elga ran while playing as a partner,

The piece of the well, on a huge scale –

In the barren deserts, the sands have cooled.

Or evening time with shabboda

Kissed girls under the plantains,

Bonfire when burning in the gorges,

A little bit of isinga ran into the fire.

That's what Bari was. Bari truth...

But it is remembered in dreams only.

A piece of air choked in the chest

The claim that one cohorts are free...

So: a tinted Cup in water
There is a legend of floods, streams,
In a broken mirror that is blurred
Khushroi has the ruins of Husni,
In today's silence, if you listen, dildor,
Yesterday's weddings have a Taron.

The great figures of Uzbek literature – Maqsud Shaykhzadeh zuvalasi, who created in the ranks of otashnafas artists such as Ghafur Ghulam and Oybek, was a singer who was littered with poetry. His works embody the effervescent echoes of the Burning Soul, which lived with great revolutionary ideals, exuberant patriotic feelings, truly creative feelings (Mirzo Ibrahimov, people's writer of Azerbaijan).

LITERATURE USED

1. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).
2. Mamurova, F. I., & ugli Abdubahabov, A. A. (2023). TWO FOLK POETS. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(3), 23-30.
3. Islomovna, M. F., & Abduvoxob o'g'li, A. A. (2023, January). Maqsud Shayxzodaning Hayoti Va Ijodi. In Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (USA) (pp. 19-20).
4. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).
5. Islamovna, Mamurova Feruza. "MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI." INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.
6. Islamovna, M. F. (2024, January). MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 189-192).
7. Islomovna, M. F. (2024). O 'ZBEK ADABIYOTINING ATOQLI NAMOYANDALARIDAN BIRI MAQSUD SHAYXZODNING "JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI" ASARI. Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 89-92.
8. Islamovna, M. F. (2024). THE CREATION OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA- AS A GOLDEN LEGACY. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 90-93.

9. Mamurova, F., & Ataxanov, O. (2024). MAQSUD SHAYXZODA HAYOTI HAQIDA. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(10), 111-116.
10. Mamurova, Feruza, and Durdona Obutjonova. "DESCRIBING MAKSUD SHAIKZODA." Current approaches and new research in modern sciences 3.4 (2024): 5-8.
11. Obutjonova, D. (2024). O‘ZBEK VA OZARBAJON XALQINING SEVIMLI SHOIRI. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(10), 103-105.